

Complex Compounds of Gold with Mercaptanic Radicles. Part II. Residual Affinities of Chlorauric Acid.

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It has been shown in Part I (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 36) that gold chloride or rather chlorauric acid reacts with ethylene dithioglycol, triethylene trisulphide and benzaethylene sulphide forming compounds in which the valency of gold varies from 2 to 5. The study has now been extended to 1:4-dithian as also to triethylene tetrasulphide.

These sulphides react with gold chloride yielding:—

Indirectly we have also a proof that when associated with metallic chlorides, the dithian is converted into triethylene trisulphide ; in other words the group $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S}$ polymerises (*cf J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 73).

The reason why in (c), the hydrogen atom has been placed under bracket is that it is really a derivative of chlorauric acid having the empirical formula $2[\text{HCl}.\text{AuCl}_3], 3(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S})_2, 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, since on neutralising its aqueous solution with potassium carbonate it effervesces and the neutral solution on evaporation yields the corresponding salt *viz.*, $\text{KAuCl}_4, 3(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S})_2, 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$. One notable feature is that if exactly the theoretical quantity, i.e., half a molecule of potassium carbonate be taken for neutralisation only the salt

(e) is obtained. If, on the other hand, one molecule of potassium carbonate be used for neutralisation, two successive crops are obtained, the first conforming to (e), i.e., $\text{KAuCl}_4 \cdot \text{HCl} \cdot 3[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$,* whereas the second to (d), i.e., $\text{KAuCl}_4 \cdot 3[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S})_2] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Cryoscopic determination of the molecular weight of (c) proves that there are altogether four ions in the compound.

Another noteworthy feature is the dropping off from triethylene trisulphide and tetrasulphide of one or more atoms of sulphur as the case may be. Thus in the latter 2 atoms of sulphur are parted with as in the compound $\text{AuCl} \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_3\text{S}_2$. The sulphur, in these cases, has been found to undergo oxidation to sulphuric acid (cf. Rây and Bose-Rây, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **121**, 1279; Mann and Pope, *ibid.*, 1923, **123**, 1179).

The action of ammonia and organic bases on these compounds has been found to be noteworthy. Thus by the action of ammonia upon (a) two compounds having the formula $\text{Au}_5\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 6(\text{NH}_3)$ and $\text{AuCl} \cdot \text{NH}_3$ respectively have been obtained. As the former explosive derivative is insoluble in all the ordinary solvents, no definite light could be thrown on its structure by recourse to physical methods. By the action of ammonia upon (c) in aqueous solution a compound having the composition, $\text{Au}(\text{NH}_3)_2 \cdot 1\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was obtained. This was also found to be explosive. These are evidently of the nature of fulminating gold compounds investigated by Raschig and others (*Annalen*, 1886, **235**, 355).

Pyridine however acting upon (a) produced the compound $\text{Au}_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \frac{1}{2}[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S})_2] \cdot \text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$. One chlorine atom and half the dithian molecule are removed and their place is taken up by a molecule of pyridine. Often complete removal of the dithian molecule takes place, as for instance, when the compound (b) is treated with pyridine, the sulphide is entirely substituted for a pyridine molecule.

Under slightly modified condition (*vide* Experimental) the product had the empirical composition, $2\text{AuCl} \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S})_2$. As it was insoluble in ordinary solvents its molecular weight could not be determined.

* The compound is really a derivative of $2\text{HCl} \cdot \text{AuCl}_3$. A corresponding compound of FeCl_3 with quinidine i.e., $2\text{HCl} \cdot \text{FeCl}_3 \cdot \text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2$ is known (Scholtz, *Ber. Deut. Pharm. Ges.*, 18, 48.)

When however (c) is similarly treated, we get $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot \text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$. Here the sulphide complex is replaced by a molecule of the base.

It thus appears that there is a close family likeness between the complex gold compounds (studied in this paper) and similar platinum compounds, so far as their action towards ammonia and organic bases is concerned. The "thio" constituents of some of these gold compounds like those of platinum, are partially or completely replaced by the base (Rây, Guha and Bose-Rây, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 958 ; Rây, Bose-Rây and Adhikari, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 467).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of $\text{HAu}_2\text{Cl}_3 (\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S})_2$ and $2 (\text{H}) \text{AuCl}_4, 3(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S})_2 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

An excess of an aqueous solution of gold chloride was added to dithian and the mixture occasionally stirred. After about 18 hours the orange precipitate was washed successively with water, alcohol, ether and benzene till the filtrate was no longer coloured. The mass was finally washed with ether and dried in a vacuum. (Found: Au, 63.49 ; Cl, 17.22. $\text{HAu}_2\text{Cl}_3, (\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S})_2$ requires Au, 63.49 ; Cl, 17.16 per cent.).

The filtrate on spontaneous evaporation in a vacuum desiccator, deposited shining orange yellow crystals. (Found: Au, 35.07 ; Cl, 25.58. $2\text{HAuCl}_4, 3(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S})_2, 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Au, 35.5 ; Cl, 25.58 per cent). Both the above substances were found to contain dithian.

Ionisability of the Compound $2\text{HAuCl}_4, 3(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S})_2, 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Observation.	Dilution (mols. per litre.)	Depression of F. P.	No. of ions (assuming complete ionisation).
I	0.08597 M	0.47°	3
II	0.03272 M	0.23°	3.6

The number of ions present at infinite dilution is therefore taken to be four.

Action of Ammonia upon $\text{HAu}_2\text{Cl}_3, (\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S})_2$.

Ammonia gas was passed through a suspension of the complex sulphide in water for about half an hour. The insoluble brown precipitate was collected, washed with water, alcohol, benzene and

ether and dried. It could not be crystallised, since it was practically insoluble in common media. It has no m. p. but explodes on heating. (Found: Au, 85·21; Cl, 6·10; N, 7·01. Au_5Cl_2 , $6(\text{NH}_3)$ requires Au, 85·06; Cl, 6·13; N, 7·25 per cent.). The preparation was repeated several times with identical results.

The filtrate on evaporation in a vacuum gave a crop of white crystals which were washed with water, alcohol and ether and dried. (Found: Au, 78·81; Cl, 14·14; N, 5·86. AuCl , NH_3 requires Au, 78·96; Cl, 14·22; N, 5·61 per cent. Sulphur was found to be absent.).

Action of Pyridine upon $\text{HAu}_2\text{Cl}_3(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S})_2$.

The substance, $\text{HAu}_2\text{Cl}_3(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S})_2$ was digested with pyridine for 15 minutes on a water-bath, when it completely went into solution. The solution was filtered and left aside when gradually a crop of white crystals separated. This was washed with a little pyridine, and dried by pressing between folds of filter paper and kept in a vacuum over sulphuric acid. The substance is very sensitive to light and is reduced when exposed to sun-light. It had no m. p. (Found: Au, 65·2, 65·31; Cl, 11·61, 11·43; N, 2·91. 4AuCl , $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S})_2$, $2\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ requires Au, 65·23; Cl, 11·75; N, 2·32 per cent.). The substance was found to contain dithian.

Action of Benzylamine upon $\text{HAu}_2\text{Cl}_3(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S})_3$.

On adding an excess of benzylamine to the substance much heat was generated. The mixture was heated on a water-bath for 15 minutes and cooled. The semi-solid mass thus obtained had a dark appearance due to portion having undergone reduction. It was extracted with absolute alcohol. Ether was then added to the filtered extract which caused precipitation of a white crystalline substance. It was washed with water to free it from benzylamine hydrochloride and dried in an amber-coloured desiccator. (Found: Au, 59·07; Cl, 10·00. AuCl ($\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{NH}_2$) requires Au, 58·31; Cl, 10·40 per cent.). Sulphur was found to be absent.

Preparation of $\text{AuCl}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S})_2$.

A mixture of dithian and an excess of an aqueous solution of gold chloride was heated on a water-bath with occasional shaking for 3-4 hours. The insoluble mass was then filtered off, washed with water, alcohol, and ether, and was extracted with hot benzene to

remove the unacted upon dithian. The residue thus purified was a pale yellow precipitate. (Found: Au, 55·31; Cl, 10·58; AuCl(C₂H₄S)₂ requires Au, 55·88; Cl, 10·00 per cent. Sulphur was found to be present.)

The aqueous filtrate deposited, on being long kept in a vacuum, orange yellow shining crystals which were identical with those previously obtained (*vide p.* 547) and had the composition 2HAuCl₄, 3(C₂H₄S)₂, 4 H₂O. It will thus be seen that chlorauric acid undergoes reduction in the previous case.

Action of Pyridine upon AuCl(C₂H₄S)₂.

(a) The compound, AuCl(C₂H₄S)₂ was kept suspended in pyridine in a dark place for half an hour. During this period, the pale yellow gold compound was gradually converted into a white substance. This was washed with pyridine, alcohol and ether and dried in an amber-coloured desiccator. (Found: Au, 62·88; Cl, 12·27. AuCl, C₅H₅N requires Au, 63·24; Cl, 11·4 per cent.). Sulphur was found to be absent. If the reaction is carried on in presence of light reduction takes place.

(b) AuCl(C₂H₄S)₂ was heated with an excess of pyridine to 60-70° until everything went into solution. The solution was filtered, cooled and diluted with ether when a white crystalline deposit was obtained. This was washed with alcohol and ether to remove pyridine and dried in a desiccator. (Found: Au, 67·44; Cl, 11·87; S, 10·07. 2[AuCl], (C₂H₄S)₂ requires Au, 67·31; Cl, 12·13; S, 10·94 per cent.). Nitrogen was found to be absent.

Preparation of KAuCl₄, 3 [(C₂H₄S)₂], 4H₂O.

To the aqueous solution of 2[HAuCl₄], 3(C₂H₄S)₂, 4H₂O molar quantity of potassium carbonate was added, carbon dioxide escaped with effervescence and the solution on concentration in a vacuum over sulphuric acid yielded yellow crystals which conform to the formula given above. (Found: Au, 24·36; Cl, 16·94; K, 5·23; S, 23·24. KAuCl₄, 3[(C₂H₄S)₂], 4H₂O requires Au, 24·33; Cl, 17·53; K, 4·82; S, 23·70 per cent.).

Preparation of HCl, KAuCl₄, 3(C₂H₄S)₂, 2H₂O.

If however in the above preparation instead of adding potassium carbonate in the molar proportion an equivalent quantity *i.e.*, $\frac{1}{2}$ K₂CO₃ be used we get the compound (H) KAuCl₅, 3(C₂H₄S)₂,

$2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in the shape of yellow crystals. (Found: Au, 23·94, 23·99, 24·03; K, 5·11; Cl, 21·78; S, 23·42. (H) $\text{KAuCl}_3, 3(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S})_2, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Au, 24·30; K, 4·94; Cl, 21·81; S, 23·72 per cent.).

It should be noticed that the molecular weight of (d) and (e) are almost the same, namely 810 and 809·5 respectively; hence the percentage of Au, K, and S come out almost the same, but the difference in the percentage of chlorine is marked. As the quantity of potassium carbonate used is half that of the previous compound an acid salt is evidently formed.

From the mother-liquor of (H) $\text{KAuCl}_3, 3(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S})_2, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ potassium chloraurate, $\text{KAuCl}_4, 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is obtained. (Found: Au, 42·74; K, 7·90; Cl, 30·07; S absent. $\text{KAuCl}_4, 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Au, 42·09; Cl, 30·34; K, 8·33 per cent.).

Preparation of $\text{AuCl}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_3\text{S}_2$.

Triethylene tetrasulphide (m.p. 104° , *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 1090) and an excess of gold chloride in water were heated on a water-bath for 7 to 8 hours with occasional shaking, when a brick-red mass was obtained. This was collected, washed with water alcohol and hot benzene to remove the uncondensed parent bodies and finally dried in a desiccator. (Found: Au, 52·03; Cl, 9·33; S, 16·82. $\text{AuCl}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_3\text{S}_2$ requires Au, 52·67; Cl, 9·38; S, 18·19 per cent.).

Action of Ammonia upon $2(\text{H})\text{AuCl}_4, 3(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S})_2, 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Ammonia gas was passed through an aqueous solution of this compound, when a brown precipitate was thrown down. This was washed with water, alcohol, ether and benzene. It was found to be highly explosive and conformed to the formula, $\text{Au}(\text{NH}_3)_2, 1\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$. (Found: Au, 75·84; N, 10·14. $\text{Au}(\text{NH}_3)_2, 1\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Au, 76·36; N, 10·85 per cent.). Both sulphur and chlorine were found to be absent.

Action of Pyridine upon $2[\text{HAuCl}_4], 3(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S})_2, 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

(a) The gold compound was digested with pyridine on a water-bath for 15 minutes when a portion went into solution leaving a mass of white crystals. The white crystals were further purified by crystallisation from water and on analysis proved to be the sulphone of dithian. Evidently the chlorine atoms set free in the reaction, acted as oxidising agent. (Found: S, 35·80; C, 25·52; H, 4·55. $\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{O}_4\text{S}_2$ requires S, 34·78; C, 26·09; H, 4·85 per cent.).

The solution on cooling deposited a crop of orange crystals. This was washed with water and dried in a vacuum desiccator. It had no m.p. but charred at about 210°. (Found: Au, 46.15; Cl, 25.97; N, 4.40; C, 21.70; H, 2.15. $\text{AuCl}_3, 1\frac{1}{2}\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ requires Au, 66.68; Cl, 25.12; N, 4.91; C, 21.33; H, 1.8 per cent.).

The mother-liquor, on spontaneous evaporation, yielded a crop of light orange crystals, which were washed with water and dried in a vacuum. (Found: Au, 42.72; Cl, 22.89. $\text{AuCl}_3, 2\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ requires Au, 42.70; Cl, 23.07 per cent.). Sulphur was proved to be absent.

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Cf. foot note, p. 5.
